

IMPROVING THE PROVISION OF ADMINISTRATIVE TERMS IN UZBEK-ENGLISH TRANSLATION DICTIONARIES

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Abstract: This article analysis and gives different problems of translations of administrative terms in English and Uzbek languages. The necessity of this issue is becoming more and more actual in these fast moving and labour exchanging world. Terminology is essential part of linguistics in translation dictionaries; there are some aspects which should be improved.

Key words: enrichment, cultural difference, translating complex terminologies, digital dictionaries.

In today’s Uzbek linguistics all field are being covered and the enlightenment period of uzbek language is connected to educated “Jadids” as a matter of the fact that “Whether someone likes it or not, our people should go without deviating from the way our jadid grandfathers showed them. Because their ideas and programs are in harmony and harmony in every way with the strategy of building a new Uzbekistan,” said Our President, Supreme Commander - in-chief, Shavkat Miromonovich Mirziyoyev [1]. Those people were who tried to improve uzbek language in the world. If the period in which they lived was very little in time and not limited to certain political events, I would call these actions of our jadidist compatriots a small renaissance [2].

Language change and enrichment of modern vocabulary is very crucial. Both languages are enriched with new words, terms and expressions over time. For example, new terms often appear in the technological, scientific and cultural fields. Modern dictionaries should include new terms and ensure their accurate translation. Difficulties in translating complex terminologies can be struggling when a user wants to apply them. In many cases, scientific, technical or legal terms do not exactly correspond to the English language in Uzbek or can have multiple meanings. Terminological dictionaries based on special manuals are needed to ensure accurate and correct translation of terms. Contextual relevance and variability of word meaning: the meaning of a word often depends on the context. Current versions of dictionaries often do not adequately reflect this aspect. Dictionaries should include examples of how words are used in different contexts. The Uzbek language is becoming increasingly recognized globally, but sometimes the quality and

completeness of existing dictionaries are limited. The international status of the Uzbek language can be strengthened by creating quality translations from English. For English language learners or translators, some dictionaries may be unclear or written in an old-fashioned style. It is important to create dictionaries that are interactive and understandable, and that meet the needs of users. In the modern world, many people use digital dictionary platforms. Currently available translation dictionaries sometimes do not meet technological requirements. Dictionaries should be developed that are integrated with artificial intelligence and support functions such as contextual analysis and voice translation.

Translations should also take cultural aspects into account. If some expressions or metaphors are not translated, they can be misunderstood. Dictionaries should provide cultural explanations and explanations. Improving dictionaries between English and Uzbek will not only facilitate language learning and translation work, but also strengthen communication and cooperation between the two languages and cultures.

1. **Corpus-Based Approach:** researchers use parallel or comparable corpora to identify accurate translations of terminologies in context. This method relies on analyzing language patterns in large datasets to ensure translations are accurate and contextually relevant [1]. It discusses the application of specialized corpora in improving terminological accuracy in translation.

2. **Cognitive and Conceptual Mapping:** This approach involves understanding the conceptual equivalence of terms between source and target languages. Researchers emphasize the cultural and semantic differences that affect terminology translation [2]. This study explores how cognitive and conceptual analysis can enhance terminological accuracy in dictionaries.

3. **Standardization of Terminologies:** Developing standardized terminology databases to ensure consistency across translations. These databases often involve collaboration with experts in specific fields [3]. It provides guidelines for standardizing terminologies and their translations.

4. **Multilingual Termbanks and Databases:** The use of termbanks like IATE (InterActive Terminology for Europe) or TermNet to support dictionary entries. These databases offer precise and verified translations across languages [4]. It highlights the role of terminological databases in dictionary development.

5. **User-Centered Approaches:** Collecting feedback from dictionary users (e.g., translators, subject matter experts) to refine and improve translations. This method focuses on real-world application and user needs [5]. This research examines the impact of user feedback on improving dictionary entries, including terminologies.

6. **AI and Machine Learning in Terminology Translation:** Utilizing artificial intelligence and machine learning to predict and generate accurate translations of

terms based on extensive linguistic data [6]. It discusses how machine learning models can enhance translation accuracy, particular for specialized terms.

7. Contextual Usage and Phraseology: Incorporating examples of terms in authentic contexts to illustrate their usage in both source and target languages [7]. It advocates for the inclusion of contextual examples in terminological dictionaries.

8. Ontological Approaches: Building ontologies that define relationships between terms and their meanings across languages to ensure accurate translations [8]. It explores ontological modeling as a framework for understanding and translating terminologies

These approaches reflect the multifaceted efforts to improve the translation of terminologies, catering to different fields, user needs, and technological advancements.

There are several problematic situations that can arise when translating English administrative terms into Uzbek. The following are some of these terms and the difficulties they face when translating them into Uzbek:

Accountability problem: This term can be translated as "accountability", but in Uzbek it often refers only to responsibility or the obligation to respond. In English, "accountability" is used in a broader sense and includes the transparency and reporting of responsibility.

Example: The manager must ensure accountability for all project tasks.

The manager must ensure accountability for all project tasks. (However, the nuance of "accountability" is not sufficiently reflected.)

2. Stakeholder

Problem: There is no clear equivalent for this term in Uzbek. It can be translated as "interested party" or "participant party", but this may not reflect the full meaning.

Example: Stakeholders must be consulted before implementing the new policy.

Stakeholders must be consulted before implementing the new policy. (This term is often used in a broader sense.)

3. Benchmarking

Problem: This term can be translated into Uzbek as "benchmarking" or "comparison of standards". However, the exact technical meaning of the term in business and management is often not fully understood.

Example: Benchmarking is a key process for improving organizational performance.

Benchmarking is a key process for improving organizational performance. (The essence of the technical process is not sufficiently expressed.)

4. Compliance

Problem: "Compliance" is often translated as "compliance with laws and regulations". However, this word, especially in business, has a broader meaning and

also denotes full compliance of the organization with internal and external regulations.

Example: The company ensures compliance with international standards.

The company ensures compliance with international standards. (There may be difficulties in expressing an even broader concept.)

5. Due Diligence

Problem: This term can be translated into Uzbek as "full investigation" or "necessary caution", but it is very specific and widely used in legal and financial processes.

Example: Conducting due diligence is crucial before finalizing the contract.

Conducting a full investigation before finalizing the contract is very important. (However, the legal nuances of this term are less expressed.)

6. Governance

Problem: This term is translated into Uzbek as "governance". However, the term "governance" usually includes transparency, compliance with rules, and stability, which can be limited to the simple word "governance".

Example: Good governance is essential for sustainable development.

Good governance is essential for sustainable development. (The broader meaning of this term is not fully reflected.)

7. Outsourcing

Problem: This term is translated as "using external resources" or "outsourced". However, it refers to the implementation of business processes through a third party, which is sometimes not fully reflected in the translation.

Example: The company decided to outsource its IT services.

The company decided to outsource its IT services to an external contractor. (The strategic nature of this process is sometimes incorrectly expressed.)

8. Audit Trail

Problem: This term can be translated as "audit trail", but its meaning is not fully understood in Uzbek. It refers to tracking all steps in an organization's financial or operational processes.

Example: Maintaining a clear audit trail is critical for accountability.

Maintaining a clear audit trail is critical for accountability. (The technical meaning may be limited.)

9. Leverage

Problem: This term can be translated as "advantage" or "tool". However, it refers to the use of opportunities in a financial or strategic sense.

Example: The company leveraged its assets to secure a loan.

The company leveraged its assets to secure a loan. (This term is used in a broader strategic sense.)

10. Sustainability

Problem: This term is translated as "sustainability", but it refers to a broader concept that includes environmental, economic, and social sustainability.

Example: Sustainability is a key goal in modern business practices.

Sustainability is a key goal in modern business practices. (The broader ecological and economic nuances are not fully covered.)

These examples show that when translating English administrative terms into Uzbek, it is necessary to take into account not only the lexical meaning, but also contextual and cultural nuances.

The following recommendations can be made for improving English-Uzbek translation dictionaries:

1. **Expand and clarify terminology:** Create specialized dictionaries by field: Develop specialized terminological dictionaries for scientific, legal, economic, and technical fields. **Update the terminology base:** Regularly enrich dictionaries with new terms and expressions.

2. **Add contextual translations:** Provide examples that show how a word or term is used in different contexts. **Classify polysemantic words:** Separate words with multiple meanings into different contexts and explain each of them.

3. **Consider cultural and connotative meanings:** Include annotations that explain the cultural and connotative meaning of the word being translated. **Explain idioms and phrases:** Explain or explain English idioms with their Uzbek equivalents.

4. **Draw on linguistics and translation theory:** Dictionaries sometimes fail to take linguistic nuances into account. **Collaborate with linguists:** Involve linguists and translation specialists in creating and editing dictionaries. **Show grammatical features of words:** Show the grammatical forms of each word, such as noun, verb, and adjective.

5. **Introduction of digital dictionaries and technologies:** Traditional dictionaries do not meet modern technological needs. **Creating digital platforms:** Developing dictionaries in the form of electronic and mobile applications.

Introduction of artificial intelligence and machine learning: Integrating dictionaries with automatic translation systems and artificial intelligence.

Contextual search function: Adding functions that allow users to find the meanings of a particular word in different contexts.

6. **Studying user needs:** Dictionaries may not meet the real needs of users. **Conducting surveys and analyses:** Studying the needs of dictionary users and adding functions that correspond to them. **Taking into account user opinions:** Taking into account feedback from users on improving the dictionary.

7. **Introducing additional features:** Many dictionaries only provide word translation, but do not provide additional features that are useful for language

learning. Show synonyms and antonyms: Provide similar or opposite meanings of a word.

Phonetic hints: Include phonetic notations that indicate the correct pronunciation of a word. Add word combinations and collocations: Show how a word is combined with other words and used.

8. Standardizing dictionaries and international cooperation: English-Uzbek dictionaries may differ from each other or may not be based on the same standards. Create standards: Align dictionaries with international lexicographic standards. Join international dictionary projects: Participate in international projects to include the Uzbek language in global terminology databases.

These recommendations will help to improve the quality of English-Uzbek dictionaries, adapt them to modern needs, and make them user-friendly.

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